

Mechanisms Underlying the Knee Adduction Moment and its Regulation: Conducive to Explaining the Aetiologies of Medial Compartment Knee Osteoarthritis

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Abstract

The knee adduction moment (KAM) is considered to be closely related to the occurrence and progression of medial compartment knee osteoarthritis (OA); however, the mechanisms underlying the KAM remain unclear. The current understanding of the KAM does not explain some clinical phenomena well. In this study, the process underlying the KAM is expounded from a biomechanical perspective, which explains the KAM based on the elastic energy in the gait. In addition, a possible linkage regulation mechanism between the ankle-subtalar joint complex (ASTC) and knee joint is put forward, and an intrinsic connection between this linkage regulation mechanism and changes in KAM is established. These discussions cannot only reasonably explain the clinical phenomena identified by the author, but also contribute to the explanation of the aetiologies of medial compartment OA from a biomechanical perspective. The author believes that all the adjustment movements that occur in an individual's gait are to maintain a stable centre of gravity (CG) and comfortable gait, and at the same time save energy consumption. A reasonable amount of KAM is conducive not only to the stability of CG in gait and comfortable advancement, but also to energy saving. Factors such as trunk inclination, pace, step width, toe-out angle, body weight, femorotibial angle, muscle strength, muscle mass, and tension of the iliotibial tract may all affect the KAM in gait, but the human body can also actively adjust KAM within a certain range through a specific regulation mechanism; the iliotibial tract plays an important role in this regulation mechanism because of its unique tension band effect. When some soft tissue structures in the human body degrade (mainly due to the decreased muscle strength of the vastus lateralis, biceps femoris, gluteus medius, and gluteus minimus, as well as the decreased muscle mass of the vastus lateralis, gluteus medius, and gluteus minimus, or the increased relaxation of the iliotibial tract), the tension band effect of the iliotibial tract does not fully manifest; therefore, the KAM will not be controlled reasonably. This causes continuously increased stress in the medial compartment of the knee joint, which may be the most important biomechanical aetiology of medial compartment knee OA.

Keywords

Knee adduction moment; Subtalar joint; Knee osteoarthritis; Biomechanics; Mechanism

Background

Osteoarthritis (OA) of the knee increases in prevalence with age.¹ Medial compartment knee OA is the most common form.²⁻⁴ The known possible aetiologies include sex, age, race, heredity, postmenopausal changes, acute and chronic trauma, weight, and lifestyle, among others,⁵ but the

decisive factors are not clear. At present, the mainstream view holds that medial compartment knee OA is closely related to the magnitude of the knee adduction moment (KAM),^{4,6-9} and the KAM in patients with medial compartment knee OA is significantly greater than that in healthy subjects.¹⁰⁻¹² Therefore, understanding the mechanisms underlying the KAM, role of the KAM, and mechanisms regulating the KAM are of decisive significance in preventing and treating medial compartment knee OA.

Mechanism of the KAM

The mechanism underlying the KAM remains unclear.¹³ Matziolis et al. believed that it is because the medial side of the knee is closer to the centre of gravity (CG), which leads to the KAM.¹⁴ Jackson et al. suggested that the KAM results from the combination of the force acting at the foot during gait (which most commonly passes medial to the centre of the knee joint) and the distance that this force acts from the centre of the knee joint (the lever arm).¹⁵ However, the above description seems to be of little help for explaining the following clinical phenomenon. Usually, the part of the shoe sole that is first worn out is on the posterolateral side of the heel. Ankle sprains are also significantly more common on the lateral side.¹⁶ However, ankle OA often occurs on the medial side.¹⁷

The following explanation seems to expound the mechanism underlying KAM more intuitively; during normal horizontal walking, because the CG is essentially stable in the coronal axis, the vertical line of the CG is always medial to the centre of pressure (COP; can be defined as the centre of all external forces acting on the plantar surface of the foot¹⁸). At a certain point in the stance phase, the resultant force, F , formed from the CG to COP can be decomposed into a vertical component, F_1 , and a horizontal component, F_2 , (Figure 1) in the coronal plane. The magnitude of the two components will change constantly during continuous walking. However, the horizontal component F_2 does not actually cause the CG to swing significantly in the coronal axis but counteracts the ground friction force during braking of the planta pedis. The ground friction force has a horizontal component f pointing to the medial side of the human body, and f and F_2 are in opposite directions and have the same magnitude, forming a force couple, and thus leading to the KAM.

During early stance, a part of ground reaction force (GRF) after heel load bearing raises the CG, leading to an increase in gravitational potential energy.¹⁰ At the same time, another part of GRF will be theoretically converted into elastic energy in the lower limbs through form changes in the muscles, ligaments, articular cartilage, and other structures (potentially even including the bones) (energy storage process).¹⁹ The elastic energy at this stage can be widely distributed in the bones and soft tissue structures of the lower limbs. The stress in the medial compartments of the knee, malleolus medialis, and medial hip joint increases due to the adduction of the whole lower limb, while the soft tissue structures on the lateral side of the lower limbs, including dynamic structures (such as the gluteus minimus, gluteus medius, tensor fasciae latae, vastus lateralis, biceps femoris, and peroneus) and static structures (such as the iliotibial tract, lateral collateral ligament, and lateral ankle ligament), jointly provide a tension to maintain the stability of the lower limbs. During mid-stance, with the adjustment of the load-bearing posture of the feet, both the longitudinal arches and the transverse arches of the feet will undergo form changes, and a part of GRF will be converted into elastic energy stored in the arches (energy storage process). During late stance, with the release of the heel load, the elastic energy stored in each structure will be

released through the recovery of limb form changes, and converted into kinetic energy for maintaining CG height and advancing the CG (energy release process).

In fact, the formation process of the KAM can be regarded as a 'pole vault effect' (PVE). Just like in pole vault, the kinetic energy formed by the athlete when running up can be converted into elastic energy by bending the pole (Figure 2). The PVE actually causes an adduction moment in the whole lower limb rather than only at the knee joint, but the stress is most concentrated at the knee joint. At the stage of elastic energy release through the restoration of the original shape of the pole, the CG of the athlete is lifted and moves forward. The form change process of the lower limbs at the late-stance stage is similar to this. At this stage, the abduction angles of the hip joints and knee joints are restored as before,²⁰ and the release of elastic energy in the lower limbs can help push the CG forward and maintain the height of the CG.

Significance of the KAM

Many studies have confirmed that KAM also exists in healthy people.^{10,11,21,22} In addition, another phenomenon has also been observed; the correlation of the thickness of the articular cartilage with the KAM is greater in the medial condyle of the femur of healthy subjects.^{23,24} These studies all show that the KAM is a normal phenomenon. Combined with the above analysis, the author believes that the KAM can be regarded as the price for maintaining a stable CG. On the other hand, a reasonable amount of elastic energy can be obtained by proper limb form changes during gait, and the elastic energy can be converted into kinetic energy for the body to advance and maintain CG height in the gait advancing stage, which cannot only save energy consumption during continuous walking, but also increase comfort of the human body during gait.

Stability of the CG

During initial stance, with the beginning of load bearing on the heel plantar surface, the PVE begins to appear, which causes the lateral part of the heel plantar surface (lateral calcaneal process) to bear a stress while forming the KAM. During the whole early stance, because of the continuous action of the PVE, the main load-bearing path of the foot gradually develops from back to front, along the lateral planta pedis, finally leading to simultaneous load-bearing of the hindfoot and forefoot. During this process, the lower limbs need to raise the height of the CG, and at the same time, the role of the PVE is gradually enhanced. In the stance phase, the main load-bearing path of the planta pedis should follow a certain curve related to gait and pace (Figure 3); however, the CG, which has an initial speed, needs to maintain stability in the coronal axis when being lifted. At the stage when the CG has not yet crossed the COP, the gradual enhancement of the PVE just matches the need to maintain stability of the CG; however, when the CG crosses the COP in the sagittal axis, if the person experiences the mid-stance according to the trend caused by the PVE, the CG will be pushed to the contralateral side of the load-bearing limb in the gait advancing stage, which will inevitably lead to CG instability; this will not only reduce walking comfort, but also increase energy consumption. Therefore, in order to maintain a stable CG, the human body must make some adjustments to balance the adduction moment of the lower limbs; the author believes that this adjustment includes two aspects: changes in the subtalar joint (STJ), as well as knee adduction and abduction.

Here, let us first demonstrate how changes in the STJ, as well as knee adduction and abduction, stabilize the CG in the coronal axis using a one-foot balance simulation test. When a

person stands on one foot and reaches a stable state, the human body will tilt toward the same side as the load-bearing limb, such that the vertical line of the CG coincides with COP, and the heel and the whole forefoot bear the weight together to maintain the a stable CG. When the CG moves, the human body will change the spatial position of talus ²⁵, as well as knee adduction and abduction through muscle adjustment, to achieve CG stability. For example, if the CG moves towards the medial side, the human body will tend to tilt towards the medial side, and with the increase in the KAM (due to the increase in F2), the talus will be immediately adjusted, undergoing pronation and plantarflexion. This will cause two effects: one is the formation of a valgus moment at the STJ and the other is the change in load-bearing from the heel and whole forefoot to the medial heel and medial forefoot. ²⁶ At the same time, it is likely that knee abduction is achieved by simultaneously strengthening the contraction of the biceps femoris, vastus lateralis, gluteus medius, and gluteus minimus. ²⁷ This will also cause two effects: one is the reduction of the KAM, and the other is the relative movement of the knee joint towards the medial side (causing the femorotibial angle to decrease). When the STJ and knee joint experience the above-mentioned changes in linkage, it can cause the COP to move towards the medial side. At this time, the valgus moment generated at the STJ and reduced adduction moment at the knee joint will force CG to move towards the lateral side, thus avoiding tilting towards the medial side. The position of the COP will then be controlled by adjusting the load-bearing posture of the foot. Finally, the CG and COP will gradually overlap in the vertical axis to stabilize the CG. If these adjustments are appropriate, the load-bearing part will revert to the heel and whole forefoot, the femorotibial angle will return to its initial position, the moment will reach balance again, and the CG will be stable again. If the adjustment is beyond the proper range, the CG will move towards the lateral side. At this time, the human body will tend to tilt towards the lateral side again, accompanied by a decrease in the KAM; thus, the talus will again undergo supination and dorsiflexion; this will cause two effects: one is the formation of a varus moment at the STJ, and the other is a change in load-bearing from the heel and whole forefoot to the lateral heel and lateral forefoot. ²⁶ Meanwhile, it is likely that knee adduction is achieved by simultaneously strengthening the contraction of the semitendinosus, semimembranosus, and gracilis (the sartorius may only participate in knee flexion); this can cause two effects: one is an increase in the KAM and the other is the relative movement of the knee joint towards the lateral side (resulting in an increased femorotibial angle). The linkage change between them can promote the relative movement of the CG towards the medial side and stabilizes CG by achieving moment balance. The above process of stabilizing the CG is like stabilizing an upright club with a fingertip; if the club is about to fall to one side, it can be stabilized again by moving the finger to the same side. In contrast, the mechanism of stabilizing the CG in the human body is more complicated and more elaborate. From this simulation experiment, the following conclusions can be drawn: the deviation of the CG from the COP in the coronal plane can lead to instability of the CG and changes in the KAM, while the human body can balance the moment of the lower limbs and maintain CG stability by actively adjusting STJ movements, as well as knee adduction and abduction. Such adjustment strength can be controlled within a certain range, and the special structure of the STJ may show its greatest physiological significance in this regulation mechanism.

STJ Movements

The talus has a special anatomical morphology. The upper part of the talus, the distal tibia, and the medial and lateral ankle together form a ginglymus joint. The lateral movement of both sides of the talus is restricted by the medial and lateral malleoli, but the malleolus and foot can perform dorsiflexion in the sagittal plane. With the subtalar joint as a peculiar single anatomic-functional entity due to its connections with the tibiotalar and Chopart's joint and the peculiar anatomical features of the talus in which forces are transmitted to structures above and below,²⁸ the spatial position of the talus will not change unless it bears weight,²⁹ and different spatial positions of the talus will produce corresponding moments, the magnitudes and directions of which are determined by the position of the CG.

Now, the author will explain the movements of the STJ from a new perspective. The leg and foot are connected as a whole by the ASTC, comprising the ankle joint and STJ; the ASTC can perform inversion and eversion movements over a small range in the coronal plane. During early stance, the load-bearing point of the heel stops moving due to ground friction, and the horizontal component, F_2 , of the resultant force from the CG to this load-bearing point will cause the distal tibia, talus, and superior calcaneus to move towards the lateral side. In contrast, the ground friction on the heel produces a horizontal component force, f , pointing towards the medial side of the human body; this force couple will cause the inversion of the ASTC, which will increase the stress on the medial side of the ASTC. Meanwhile, the lateral ligament structure of the ankle joint will remain tense; the knee joint will also undergo adduction and the KAM will increase due to the PVE. At this stage, the ASTC inversion and knee adduction are mainly passive reactions (Figure 4-a). With the progression of gait, when the CG crosses the COP in the sagittal axis (the author defines this as the 'inflection point'), in order to stabilize the CG, the spatial position of the talus will change to adjust the ASTC moment.^{20,30} However, because there is no muscle attached across the whole talus, the changes in its spatial position will not take place spontaneously but can only be realized by the relative position change and stress adjustment of the adjacent tarsus and calcaneus. At this time, the talus plays a role similar to that played by the head when an athlete pushes the ball against the top of their head to prevent the ball from falling. The head is only responsible for contacting the ball, while the neck controls the movement of the head. Similarly, the movement direction of the adjacent tarsus and force applied to the talus may be adjusted mainly through the tension adjustment movements of several groups of agonist-antagonist muscle pairs, such as the peroneus longus and tibialis posterior; when the adjacent tarsus moves, the calcaneus also turns over simultaneously.²⁵ This indirectly changes the spatial position of the talus, thus realizing the changes in the ASTC moment and plantar load-bearing mode, accompanied by the linkage changes in knee abduction.²⁰ Through these changes, the CG can be stabilized, and CG will not be displaced during gait advancement. In this adjustment process, the main load-bearing path of the planta pedis will no longer follow the lateral path before the inflection point, but will gradually move towards the medial and anterior parts such that the weight load is spread across the whole forefoot (Figure 3). At this time, the KAM is reduced, and the tension of the medial and lateral ankle ligament structures is essentially balanced. At this stage, ASTC eversion and knee abduction are active adjustments (Figure 4-b). There is also a possibility that the medial ankle ligament will be tense, while the lateral ankle ligament will be loose. When a person is standing on one foot, if the CG moves towards the medial side, the talus will undergo greater pronation and plantarflexion than those during the gait advancement stage under adjustment movements of the corresponding agonist-antagonist muscles, thus forming a larger valgus moment

at the ASTC, to balance the increase in the KAM caused by the CG moving towards the medial side. At the same time, the abduction linkage changes will also occur in the knee joint, which in turn will cause compliance changes in the pelvis and spine (described in detail below), such that the position of the CG moves relatively towards the lateral side. At this stage, ASTC eversion and knee abduction can also be classified as active adjustments (Figure 4-c). Patients with medial compartment knee OA show a more pronated foot type, which is also because a larger KAM requires the ASTC to provide a larger abduction moment to achieve balance.³¹ From the above analysis, it can be seen that moment changes not only occur in the STJ, but that only synchronous changes of the STJ and ankle joint can produce moment changes at the ankle. Therefore, the author uses the term ASTC here.

The changes in the ASTC moment depend on the changes in the spatial position of the talus, but the latter does not start only after weight loading of the forefoot (in most cases, this will happen when the inflection point comes), because this will cause redundant energy consumption and CG instability during gait. In other words, forefoot loading is not a necessary condition for the spatial position changes of the talus, and the muscle movements of the lower limbs are not determined by the spatial position of the talus; however, the opposite is true. This may challenge our existing understanding.^{25, 26, 29, 32} In continuous gait, the deviation of the CG will affect the timing of the inflection point, such that the inflection point can appear either early or late, and is dynamically adjusted according to the balance demand of the CG. The author believes that all movements during gait occur in light of the stability of the CG. In addition, the spatial position of the talus is not actively adjusted before the inflection point, which is not because the human body does not have this ability. In the author's opinion, it is most likely that this tai chi-style compliance saves more energy and makes the human body more comfortable. Of course, this analysis needs to be supported by corresponding biomechanical tests.

In fact, with the spatial position changes of the talus, the foot also gains another important function; with the pronation and plantarflexion of the talus, the height of the medial longitudinal arch of the foot decreases, the first metatarsal head descends and moves forward,²⁵ the transverse arch also sinks, and the distance between the first metatarsal head and the fifth metatarsal head increases. On the one hand, these changes can increase the stability of foot load-bearing. On the other hand, the changes in these bony structures are matched with the prolongation and tension increase in a large number of plantar soft tissue structures such as the muscles, tendons, and ligaments. This process is not only a process in which the arch plays a buffering role, but also a process in which gravitational potential energy is converted into elastic energy.³³ The elastic energy stored in the arch at this stage is converted into the driving force to move forward in the gait advancing stage.

Interpretation of the KAM Waveform Diagram

Many studies have shown that the waveform of the KAM has two peaks in the stance phase, known as the early-stance KAM and late-stance KAM. According to the above explanation, the author understands the origin of the two peaks in the KAM waveform diagram as follows. During early stance, the PVE after weight-loading of the heel causes the early-stance KAM; thus, the peak early-stance KAM appears when the CG crosses the COP; with the CG moving forward (F2 declines, accompanied by ASTC eversion and knee abduction regulation), the KAM begins to decline. However, after entering mid-stance, the contralateral lower limb enters the swing phase.

Therefore, the KAM does not disappear completely when the load-bearing limb is bearing the weight alone. After entering late stance, with the heel off the ground, the elastic energy of the load-bearing limb formed in the early stage begins to release, and forms the late-stance KAM under the joint action of the force propulsion by the triceps surae. As for the late-stance peak KAM, it is speculated that it may be result of the combination of the triceps force peak and elastic energy release.

Answers for the Questions

Based on the above discussion, the author's question at the beginning of the article can be answered. The posterolateral part of the shoe heel wears out first because the initial stance stress is most concentrated there, while the contact area is the smallest, which causes the local pressure to increase significantly. At the same time, the process of balancing F_2 and f under the action of the PVE may also cause the shoe heel to suffer certain sliding friction. Lateral ankle sprains are more common than medial ankle sprains because the PVE causes the inversion of the ASTC during early stance, and the tension of the lateral ankle ligament is high. At this stage, the usual load-bearing part of the foot is not in complete contact with the floor, and load-bearing is more concentrated on the lateral plantar surface of the heel. At this time, the stability of the ankle is poor. At the same time, the STJ is still in its passive reaction stage, and the tension of the peroneus is insufficient; therefore, it is difficult to make timely adjustments in case of unexpected occurrences. Ankle joint OA often occurs on the medial side because the stress in the medial ankle compartment is concentrated during early stance,³⁴ while the stress in the medial and lateral ankle compartments is essentially equal during the mid and late stance.

Factors Influencing the KAM

In normal gait, a KAM is inevitable, and the magnitude of the KAM will change if it is influenced by certain factors. According to the existing research results, the author divides the factors that may affect the magnitude of KAM into controllable factors, such as leaning of the trunk, pace, step width, and toe-out angle, and uncontrollable factors, such as body weight, femorotibial angle, maximum muscle strength, muscle mass, and tension of the iliotibial tract. Reasonable regulation of controllable factors may help reduce the KAM to a certain extent, but will often bring about related changes in the motor system. Therefore, these adjustments are probably just a stopgap measure, and the changes in uncontrollable factors are generally the primary factors causing changes in the KAM. Therefore, measures to improve uncontrollable factors are key to reversing the situation.

Regulatory Mechanism of the KAM

Trunk inclination

Current research has confirmed that tilting the trunk towards the load-bearing limb during gait can reduce the KAM, and a larger tilting angle can achieve greater KAM reduction.³⁵ This KAM regulation mechanism makes the CG move towards the lateral side relative to the COP by tilting the trunk, thus reducing F_2 . However, this reduces walking efficiency and gait comfort. Although this adjustment has not been found to have a harmful effect on the ankle joint moment, hip joint moment, or knee joint flexion moment,³⁶ whether it has adverse effects on the spine due to changing the spine force line requires further study.

Pace

It is generally believed that reducing walking pace will reduce the KAM; however, this is not necessarily true. Pace reduction can be achieved by reducing the step length or step frequency. Reducing the step length can reduce fluctuation of the CG and reduce the knee joint force of the CG crossing the tibial plateau during the COP stage. However, simply reducing the step frequency will impair the continuous movement of the CG and the fluctuation of the CG may increase. In addition, in the gait advancing stage, the release of elastic energy from the lower limbs cannot be well synchronized with the force exerted by the triceps surae, so it may be necessary to push the CG with greater force, which will lead to changes in the KAM. Therefore, if the adjustment actions in these gaits are not accurately restricted, the changes in KAM will be difficult to predict;^{10,12,20-22} the same is the case with an increase in pace.

Step width

With the increase in step width, the distance between the COP and CG in the coronal axis usually increases, which will lead to an increase in the horizontal component, F₂. In addition, as the step width exceeds the distance between the two hip joints, the lateral swing of the body will also increase during walking, and the swing of the CG will also increase the horizontal component, F₂. These above factors then jointly lead to an increase in the KAM. On the other hand, with the decrease in stability caused by the increase in the lateral swing of the CG, the regulatory ability of the human body to stabilize the CG through actively increasing ASTC eversion and knee abduction will also be enhanced, which will reduce the KAM. Therefore, if no accurate restriction is applied, the change to the KAM caused by a step width increase will be difficult to estimate.^{37,38} Step width reduction is special. On the one hand, F₂ can be reduced by making the COP close to CG in the coronal axis, but on the other hand, ASTC eversion will occur with a reduction in step width; the resulting ASTC eversion moment would require increased KAM to maintain the stability of the CG, otherwise the CG will swing towards the medial side; therefore, the influence of reducing step width on the KAM is uncertain.³⁹

Toe-out angle

Increasing the toe-out angle is a commonly used self-selected gait adjustment method for patients with medial compartment knee OA. Generally, this self-selected method will help reduce the KAM; however, but increasing the toe-out angle will shift the task of stabilizing the CG on the sagittal axis, which originally should be controlled by ankle flexion and extension. This increases the role of the ASTC, resulting in more complicated changes. For example, slightly leaning the body forward and backward during gait will cause changes in the CG position in the sagittal axis. With the increase in toe-out angle, the CG can no longer be stabilized only by dorsiflexion and plantarflexion of the ankle joint, but the ASTC is required to participate more in adjusting the stability of the CG. The moment change caused by ASTC movement will cause a linked reaction in knee joint and change in the KAM. In addition, limb muscle tension will also affect ASTC and knee joint movement; generally, maintaining moderate tension will be more conducive to reducing the KAM. Therefore, the moment changes and its adjustment movements caused by changes in the toe-out angle are very complex; hence, it is often difficult to define every condition accurately in gait research, which may lead to inconsistent or even contradictory research results.^{38,40,41} A small

reduction in the toe-out angle may not have a meaningful impact on the KAM, while a large reduction in the toe-out angle will generally increase the KAM.^{41,42}

Body weight

Body weight has a direct effect on the KAM. Generally, a reduction in body weight reduces the horizontal component, F₂, consequently reducing the KAM,⁴³ while an increase in body weight has the opposite effect.²⁰ However, the effects of weight gain mainly from an increase in muscle mass leading to a corresponding increase in muscle strength on the KAM should be clarified by further study.

Femorotibial angle

From a physical perspective, there is no doubt that the femorotibial angle directly affects the magnitude of the KAM, with a greater femorotibial angle leading to a greater KAM.⁴⁴ The reduction in the femorotibial angle following osteotomy can reduce the KAM, and reasonable overcorrection can make the Mikulicz line under the influence of the PVE more central instead of moving towards the medial side, thus achieving better long-term outcomes.⁴⁴⁻⁴⁷ However, it must be noted that, in theory, there should be a matching soft tissue structure in the basic femorotibial angle of each individual after development. For example, if a child with rickets has genu varus deformity, the soft tissue structure controlling the KAM in his body in adulthood needs to be more developed than that of healthy people, so that the KAM can be controlled within a reasonable range. Therefore, it seems unreasonable to directly judge the magnitude of the KAM according to the femorotibial angle.

Wedge-shaped insole

The use of lateral wedge-shaped insoles is often studied as a corrective method that may reduce the KAM by reducing the femorotibial angle. At present, most related studies suggest that lateral wedge-shaped insoles can slightly reduce the peak KAM,⁴⁸ but the measurement results are unstable, and even daily measurement results will vary greatly.⁴⁹ This may be related to the strength actively controlled by the subjects. During initial stance, if flat insoles are used, heel touchdown should be jointly supported by the calcaneal tuberosity bottom and lateral calcaneal process (Figure 5a); however, lateral wedge-shaped insoles will make the heel stress concentrate more on the lateral calcaneal process, which will make the subject feel reduced stability in the ankle joint, and leading to active adjustment of ASTC eversion (under the joint action of PVE, ASTC is not necessarily in a de facto everted state), such that the bottom of the calcaneal tuberosity will continue to participate in load-bearing, thereby improving the stability of the ankle joint (Figure 5b). Adjusting ASTC eversion will also force the knee joint to always maintain the corresponding abduction linkage reaction state, thus reducing the KAM. If the subject's intensity of active adjustment is low (e.g. the nerve sensitivity of the subject's heels is reduced or the subject actively controls the adjustment strength because they are not adapted to the everted state caused by the insoles), then the above adjustment process will slow down before the inflection point appears, and the heel under the action of the PVE still maintain load-bearing mainly on the lateral calcaneal process (Figure 5c). At this time, the influence of lateral wedge-shaped insoles on the KAM is relatively slight.

However, regardless of the degree of adjustment, lateral wedge-shaped insoles will significantly increase the pressure on the lateral heel.⁴⁹ Under conditions with the same weight, gait, and other factors, reducing the contact area will bring increase pressure. Lateral wedge-shaped insoles will cause the load-bearing part of the heel to move towards the lateral side and be limited to the lateral calcaneal process, resulting in an increase in lateral heel pressure. Moreover, it should be noted that during early stance, the effect of the PVE will be in opposition to the lateral movement of the CG, thus maintaining CG stability; after using lateral wedge insoles, the trend of the CG being pushed towards the medial side will be aggravated. Therefore, when the inflection point appears, the human body needs to control the stability of the CG through a more powerful linkage reaction of ASTC eversion and knee abduction. Regulation at this stage is inevitable, otherwise the CG will shift towards the medial side. This is the reason why the magnitude of the decrease in the late-stance peak KAM observed in these studies is usually more significant than that in early-stance peak KAM.⁴⁸

When using lateral wedge-shaped insoles combined with a bandage, the bandage forces the lateral wedge-shaped insoles to form a whole with the planta pedis, such that the adjustment in the foot's load-bearing mode is directly transferred to the shoe sole. Only relying on the contact of the lateral edge of the shoe sole at the early stage of load bearing will lead to reduced stability of the ankle joint. The ASTC eversion trend caused by the combined action of the PVE on this basis will make this eversion instability very serious (Figure 5d). Therefore, the ASTC will be forced to adjust to the everted state immediately, meaning that the shoe sole will be closely attached to the ground, maintaining the stability of the ankle joint (Figure 5e). At this time, the abduction linkage reaction of the knee joint will be enhanced accordingly. Even in the static standing position, this relatively strong adjustment mode is necessary, so lateral wedge insoles combined with bandage can be observed to reduce the femorotibial angle.⁵⁰

Maximum muscle strength, muscle mass, and tension of the iliotibial tract

The generation of the PVE relies on tension in soft tissues. Theoretically, the functional decline of lower limb dynamic soft tissues caused by any reason, such as muscle atrophy or muscle strength decline from reduced activities, disuse, or neuromuscular diseases, may all reduce the human body's ability to actively control the PVE, and affect the stability of the lower limbs, resulting in an increased KAM. Therefore, for the existing trend of increasing KAM, although the human body will actively enhance muscle movement to slow down its progression,⁵¹ the decrease in maximum muscle strength will inevitably weaken this control. Moreover, physical exercise has been proven to be effective in relieving pain and improving function in patients with OA.⁵² Patients with knee OA patients demonstrated an increase in the KAM after taking anti-inflammatory drugs, while the KAM tended to decrease when no anti-inflammatory drugs were used;⁵³ this phenomenon reflects the control of the KAM through muscle strength. Therefore, the decrease in maximum muscle strength will influence the regulation of the KAM.

Among static soft tissues, the iliotibial tract has the greatest influence on the KAM. This physiological structure is not found in carnivores,⁵⁴ why is it possessed by humans? Yount observed that the contracture of the iliotibial tract in patients with poliomyelitis can lead to tibia valga.⁵⁵ Beals also pointed out that hip abduction contracture may occur if the iliotibial tract is fixed to the femur when amputating above the knee joint.⁵⁶ The above observations support the fact that the iliotibial tract is an important stabilizing structure of human lower limbs, and it can be

inferred that the iliotibial tract can limit genua varus. Therefore, the iliotibial tract may be extremely important for the control of the KAM. In anatomy, the iliotibial tract is formed by the coalescence of the fascial investments of the tensor fascia femoris, gluteus maximus, and gluteus medius,⁵⁷ and extends downward after passing through the superficial surface of the greater trochanter, with its distal end ending at Gerdy's tubercle. The iliopatellar band anatomically connects the anterior aspect of the iliotibial tract and femur to the patella, and the iliotibial tract acts as an anterolateral ligament of the knee. Biomechanical studies have proven that the iliotibial tract is strong enough to provide anterolateral stability to the tibia.⁵⁷ Therefore, there may be a mechanism as follows, in the stance phase, through the joint action of the anterior part of gluteus medius, the anterior part of gluteus minimus, and the lateral femoral muscle, the femur will undergo pronation, which will cause the offset at the greater trochanter to increase, increasing the tension of the iliotibial tract above and below the superficial surface of the greater trochanter. At the same time, the tension of the iliotibial tract will be increased by increasing the transverse diameter of the muscles after the above-mentioned muscles tighten.⁵⁸ In this way, the iliotibial tract will play the role of a tension band, which can both stabilize the hip joint and control genu varus (Figure 6), while muscle mass will play the role of an auxiliary strengthening tension band.

It has been found that simultaneous strength training for the hip abductor and quadriceps muscle can alleviate pain, and increase function and quality of life in knee OA patients earlier than strength training for the quadriceps muscle alone,⁵⁹ which is strong support for the suggested role of the iliotibial tract as a tension band. Brouwer et al. found that during the one-year follow-up period after the operation, closed wedge osteotomy had less correction loss angle than open wedge osteotomy in the treatment of medial knee OA.⁶⁰ This may be precisely because open wedge osteotomy will reduce the tension of the iliotibial tract, and the human body cannot make adaptive changes to restore the optimal tension of the iliotibial tract in a short time after surgery; however, closed wedge osteotomy may increase the tension of the iliotibial tract, thus enhancing the function of the iliotibial tract in limiting genua varus.

In addition, it is still unclear whether the degree of relaxation in the iliotibial tract is regulated by hormone levels in the body. Research has confirmed that relaxation of the anterior cruciate ligament in female athletes increases during menstruation, which leads to an increase in the incidence of sports injuries.⁶¹ Whether the iliotibial tract is also affected and how menopause affects the iliotibial tract require more research. Therefore, the author believes that the weakened function of the iliotibial tract as a tension band may be the most important biomechanical factor leading to medial compartment knee OA.

Compliance Changes in the Pelvis and Spine

During continuous walking, in addition to regulating the knee joint torque, the tension band regulation mechanism of the iliotibial tract will also further cause compliance changes in the pelvis and spine. In the stance phase, when the femur undergoes pronation, the iliacus attached to the lesser trochanter will be pulled and drives the pelvis to move. The tensor fasciae latae will maintain synchronous movement, causing the pelvis to tilt forward, rotate, and descend (descent of the pelvis may also be related to the PVE function because the CG is located above the acetabulum).⁶² On the other hand, the spine may be affected by the joint action of the psoas major, psoas minor, and quadratus lumborum (both the psoas minor and quadratus lumborum end in the pelvis and can indirectly drive the movements of the lumbar spine through pelvic inclination),

resulting in lateroflexion and pronation of the lumbar spine. The advantages of this synchronous movement may be that it not only causes a slight lateral movement of the CG (reducing the KAM by reducing F2), but also make the long head of the biceps femoris, which is attached to the ischial tubercle, to be pulled proximally due to anterior pelvic tilt, while the distal end of biceps femoris ends at the caput fibulae. From a biomechanical perspective, this structure can affect the magnitude of the KAM. Therefore, the author speculates that the above-mentioned movements are conducive not only to the regulation of the KAM, but also to the mutual conversion of various types of energies and improving comfort during gait. Of course, the head is generally kept as stable as possible in gait through the compensatory movements of the cervical vertebrae.

Discussion

Knee osteoarthritis is a leading contributor to disability worldwide; ⁶³ thus, it is of great significance to elucidate the pathogenesis of this disease. After mechanical analysis and logical reasoning, the author believes that the biomechanical aetiology of medial compartment knee OA is probably mainly due to a deterioration in the strength of lower limb soft tissue structures or the relatively reduced functionality of lower limb soft tissue structures due to weight increase, which leads to an increased KAM. When the KAM starts to increase, the human body will adjust through various voluntary or involuntary adjustment methods (such as enhancing muscle contraction, and adjusting gait and body posture), but all adjustment methods may bring about reduced gait comfort and increased energy consumption. Therefore, treatment of the primary cause of medial compartment knee OA is the most critical measure. When doctors find that patients have hallux valgus, flat foot, plantar fasciitis, pronated foot type, increased anterior pelvic tilt (increased lumbosacral angle), scoliosis, or rotation deformity, they need to consider whether these conditions are related to the progression of medial compartment knee OA or are compensatory movements of the motion systems adjacent to the knee joint. If we only focus on the local treatment of the foot and spine, it may lead to failed treatment or other subsequent pathological changes. The author believes that the above discussion may play a helpful role in related research fields. Some viewpoints in this paper also lack the support of related biomechanical tests and should be proven in further research.

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Figures and legends

Figure 1: Decomposition of the resultant force formed from the CG to the COP

At a certain moment when the load is formed, the resultant force, F , formed from the CG to the COP can be decomposed into two components in the coronal plane: vertical component, F_1 , and horizontal component, F_2 . The frictional force from the ground on the planta pedis also has a horizontal component, f , pointing medially. f and F_2 are opposite in direction and have the same magnitude, forming a force couple, and thus leading to the KAM.

Figure 2: About the pole vault effect

In pole vault, athletes gain kinetic energy through running. After the lower end of the pole is placed into a slot, the kinetic energy from the human body bends the pole. The kinetic energy is converted into elastic energy, seen as the pole bending. The elastic energy is then converted back into kinetic energy to raise and advance the human body after restoring the original shape of the pole.

Fig. 3: Schematic diagram of the changes in plantar load-bearing path during gait

The solid line predicts the main load-bearing path during normal gait, and the dotted line predicts the load-bearing path that has not been adjusted by the ASTC and knee joint linkage reaction mechanism. After the emergence of the inflection point, the two diverge.

Fig. 4: Rotational movements of the ASTC in different states

a: During initial stance, the ASTC will be everted due to the action of the PVE, and the lateral ankle ligament will remain tense at this time.

b: During mid-stance, in order to stabilize the CG, the ASTC has been adjusted to an approximately centred position, and the tension in the ligaments at the medial and lateral malleoli is basically the same.

c: After balance is reached when standing on one foot, if the CG moves towards the medial side again, the ASTC will be adjusted to the everted state to balance the moment and stabilize the CG. At this time, the medial ankle ligament is tense.

Fig. 5: Different states of the calcaneus and ASTC during early stance when using different insoles

a: When using flat insoles, because of the PVE, the bottom of the calcaneal tuberosity and the lateral calcaneal process bear the stress together, and the ASTC is in an inverted state.

b: When using lateral wedge-shaped insoles, the stress on the bottom surface of the heel is unbalanced due to the increased stress on the lateral calcaneal process. After the eversion adjustment by the ASTC, the load on the bottom surface of the calcaneal tuberosity is increased, thus enhancing the stability of the ankle joint.

c: When using lateral wedge-shaped insoles, if the intensity of the active ASTC adjustment is insufficient, the heel, under the action of the PVE, keeps load bearing mainly on the lateral calcaneal process.

d: When using lateral wedge-shaped insoles with combined bandage, the lateral wedge-shaped insoles and heel are forced to form a whole. During the initial stance, the lateral edge of the heel will first touch the ground and bear weight, which will lead to a significant decline in the stability of the ankle joint.

e: When using lateral wedge-shaped insoles with combined bandage, the ASTC will be forced to adjust to an everted state after weight loading, so that the shoe sole will be closely attached to the ground to maintain stability of the ankle joint.

Fig. 6: Working principle of the iliotibial tract functioning as a tension band

In the load-bearing phase, the femur undergoes pronation after the anterior part of gluteus medius, the anterior part of anterior gluteus minimus, and the vastus lateralis jointly tighten, which increases the offset at the greater trochanter and tenses the iliotibial tract on the superficial surface of the greater trochanter to increase, which can play the role of a tension band. At the same time, the muscles located in the deep surface of the iliotibial tract become thicker and hardened after contraction, which can also strengthen the function of the tension band. This not only stabilizes the hip joint, but also limits genu varus.